

My point is valid, yours is not: Myside bias in reasoning about abortion

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ABSTRACT

The study explores whether people are more inclined to accept a conclusion that confirms their prior beliefs and reject one they personally object to even when both follow the same logic. Most of the prior research in this area has relied on the informal reasoning paradigm; in this study, however, we applied a formal reasoning paradigm to distinguish between cognitive and motivational mechanisms leading to myside bias in reasoning on value-laden topics (in this case abortions). Slovak and Polish (N = 387) participants indicated their attitudes toward abortion and then evaluated logical syllogisms with neutral, pro-choice, or pro-life content. We analysed whether participants' prior attitudes influenced their ability to solve these logically identical reasoning tasks and found that prior attitudes were the strongest predictor of myside bias in evaluating both valid and invalid syllogisms, even after controlling for logical validity (the ability to solve neutral syllogisms) and previous experience of logic.

Keywords: myside bias; belief bias; formal reasoning; motivated reasoning

Introduction

We have all experienced frustration when discussing controversial issues with people holding opposing opinions – it seems that no argument is persuasive enough, and that our opponents stubbornly and illogically stick to their mistaken positions. (It is highly probable they feel the same way about us.) We often assume that our position is, or should be, so obvious and self-evident that we should not even be asked to defend it. In this paper we want to explore how the values we hold and which manifest themselves in our attitudes towards certain controversial topics blind us from acknowledging the same logic in our opponents' arguments. In other words, how does reasoning in which the same logic is applied appear justified in one context but not in another?

People often have difficulty in objectively judging arguments that run counter to their strong beliefs, attitudes, and values. Various research paradigms have shown that people look only for evidence that confirms their already-held opinions or supports their prior beliefs (Baron, 1995; Betsch & Haberstroh, 2005; Nickerson, 1998). This inability to decouple one's beliefs and select arguments and conclusions that favour our already held beliefs interferes with good thinking in almost every context (Nickerson, 1998).

This tendency for people to seek confirmation rather than disconfirmation of what they already believe is usually referred to as confirmation bias (Nickerson, 1998; Sternberg & Sternberg, 2012). However, confirmation bias has been used in the psychological literature to refer to a variety of phenomena, so it is worth briefly describing the terminology. In his review of studies on confirmation bias Nickerson (1998) states that he understands the term to refer to a “generic concept that subsumes several more specific ideas that connote the inappropriate bolstering of hypotheses or beliefs whose truth is in question” (p.175). More specific types of confirmation bias are belief bias and myside bias. Myside bias occurs when people evaluate, generate, and

test evidence in a manner which is biased towards their prior attitudes and opinions. Belief bias, on the other hand, occurs when we accept or reject the conclusion of an argument based on its un/believability. In contrast to myside bias, which concerns reasoning biased towards personal opinions or stances, belief bias arises from people's factual knowledge about the world (Macpherson & Stanovich, 2007). The terminology may be a little misleading because, rather ironically, myside bias is more about reasoning that accords with personal, more subjective, beliefs (e.g. I believe that abortion is morally wrong), while belief bias is more about reasoning that accords with what we believe to be true about the world and what is usually objectively true (e.g. Men cannot get pregnant, therefore any conclusion containing this possibility is not believable). Hence, while many researchers use the terms interchangeably, we consider the main difference to lie in the personal relevance of the content. Belief bias occurs when the validity and believability of the conclusions come into conflict. Believability relates to knowledge about the world rather than to our inner beliefs or values, while myside bias specifically concerns our personal beliefs, attitudes, and opinions and brings greater subjectivity. Thus myside bias can be seen as a specific subset of belief bias that is related to more personal issues. We will try to avoid confusion by referring to myside bias as being influenced by attitudes (i.e. the acceptability of the conclusion given the person's attitude toward the topic) and belief bias as being influenced by prior beliefs (i.e. the believability of the conclusion given the known facts about the world). Furthermore, we need to remember that in our study we have used statements with normative content involving obligations ("should") and thus the reasoning process has been shifted into the sphere of deontic, or more specifically, imperative logic. Consequently such expressions are often considered to be neither truth nor false. This in turn means that such expressions cannot, at least according to the classic Platonic

definition, be elements of knowledge understood as "justified true belief". Therefore, as it would be difficult to refer to the "believability" of the conclusions (meaning sentences congruent with previous knowledge) we will consistently use the term "acceptable" instead¹.

Mixing normative content with deontic logic in this way can cause problems in debates about issues that stir up a lot of emotion because they touch on our basic values and can be particularly heated, such as discussions about abortion. Such issues tend to divide us, mainly because they concern differences in the sets of values liberals and conservatives hold (Haidt, 2012). Abortion is an issue that almost everyone has an opinion on and tends to provoke strong emotions on both sides (for pro-lifers and for pro-choicers), making it especially suitable for studies of myside bias. It is more value-laden than for example attitudes toward smoking, and less-culturally specific than for example climate change or evolution (in Eastern Europe despite the high prevalence of religion and conservatism, religious people acknowledge the theories of evolution and that global warming is a result of human activity, and there is little controversy on these issues).

Our main aim was to explore whether people are more inclined to accept a conclusion that confirms their attitudes and reject one they personally object to even when both follow the same logical pattern. Although we concentrated on a real-life controversial issue, we applied a formal reasoning paradigm (syllogisms with neutral pro-choice or pro-life content) to distinguish between the cognitive and motivational mechanisms that lead to myside bias in reasoning on value-laden topics, and then we analysed whether the participants' prior attitudes influenced their ability to solve these

¹ We are not claiming here that myside bias cannot be related to sentences that are either true or false. We are simply suggesting that once a sentence has no logical value, it cannot be considered to be either true or false and thus believable.

logically identical reasoning tasks. The difference between the syllogisms traditionally used in the belief bias paradigm and the ones used in our study is that validity and believability enter into conflict in the traditional ones, while in ours the conclusion may or may not be congruent with the attitudes (example syllogisms are to be found in Table 1). Also, in our study the samples consist of participants from Slovakia and Poland, who are traditionally more conservative than the more liberal college students who make up the samples typically used in other research (Henrich, Heine, & Norenzayan, 2010).

Moreover, abortion is very topical in Slovakia and Poland and both countries share many similarities in regard to abortion attitudes (e.g. the predominance of Catholicism², Slavic culture, post-communism, a preference for populist leaders, the call for ever stricter abortion laws³, etc.), but differ substantially in other ways, such as the nature of their abortion laws. For example, Slovakia has a relatively liberal abortion law that enables women to terminate a pregnancy in the first 12 weeks regardless of the reason, while Poland is one of six European countries with the most restrictive abortion laws, allowing abortions to be performed only in a very narrow range of situations, namely rape, risk to the mother's life or serious foetal harm. Although doctors can invoke the "conscience clause" in both countries and refuse to perform abortions, in practice this means there are large areas of Poland where hospitals perform no abortions.

² According to the 2011 Slovak and Polish censuses, Catholics accounted for 62% and 87.5% of the populations respectively; thus we can expect our participants to display more conservative and pro-life attitudes.

³ For example, in 2015 ten members of the Slovak parliament voted for a law that would send women to prison for 5 to 12 years for undergoing an abortion or for having undergone assisted reproduction. (The law was not passed and those who voted for the law were subjected to great public criticism and mocked on social networks.) Similarly, in Poland a law was proposed in 2016 that would completely ban abortion. The response was "Black Monday", a national strike. There are also initiatives to outlaw in-vitro fertilisation and assisted reproduction.

The final reason for selecting abortion as the controversial topic for our study is that we can then compare our results with other results on myside bias produced using other research paradigms (Baron, 1995; Stanovich & West, 1997, 1998). Syllogisms do not provide as much space for subjective interpretation as arguments do. The ability to decouple our prior beliefs and attitudes from our evaluation of the arguments and evidence is fundamental to critical thinking (Macpherson & Stanovich, 2007). In the modern and increasingly multicultural world (in which different cultural values can clash), where we have instant access to information, our ability to reason well, to distinguish between correct and incorrect information, and to evaluate the facts and arguments openly and without bias are essential skills for dealing with the world around us.

First, we will briefly review the literature on myside bias findings, then we will consider the current literature on belief bias and provide a rationale for using syllogisms to study myside bias.

How attitudes affect informal reasoning

One of the first studies of myside bias examined the quality of the arguments students produced in relation to early abortion (first day of pregnancy) and showed that people tend to give more arguments supporting the attitude they favour than against the opposing attitude (myside bias) (Baron, 1995).

Stanovich and West (1997) expanded on and formalised this approach by devising the Argument Evaluation Test (AET). They studied individual differences in the ability to evaluate the quality of an argument independent of one's feelings and attitudes toward the topic. They found that the ability to resist myside bias is linked to higher cognitive abilities and actively open-minded thinking. In a later study Stanovich

and West (1998) examined the relationship between the measures of myside bias (AET) and belief bias in syllogistic reasoning. They found moderate correlations (.293–.340) between the ability to correctly solve conflicting syllogisms (syllogisms in which validity and believability were in conflict) and the beta weight for argument quality in the AET.

Focusing specifically on reasoning about a controversial topic such as abortions, Stanovich and West (2008; Study 2) replicated Baron's (1995) results using a slightly modified method of reasoning about abortions to improve the coherence and naturalness of the arguments. Similarly to Baron (1995), Stanovich and West also found evidence of one-side bias, that is, that the arguments from one side (even the opposing side) are favoured and considered better.

Yet another approach to studying how prior attitudes affect our reasoning was employed by Klaczynski (2000), who studied how adolescents' prior theories (beliefs) led to motivated reasoning in support of their preconceived theories. He focused on two myside biases: social class and religion. He found reasoning biases for both social class and religion, but only myside bias for religion. These results suggest that participants use double standards when judging studies depending on the correspondence between the study's conclusion and the person's prior attitudes. If the study findings confirm our prior theory, we rely on intuition and accept it at face value, but when the findings challenge our hypothesis, we engage in more analytical processing either to rationalise our theory, or to reject the new evidence based on more detailed scrutiny.

Similarly to Stanovich and West (1997, 1988), Thompson and Evans (2012) examined whether the belief bias that occurs in both formal reasoning (using syllogisms) and informal reasoning (using various kinds of argument evaluation) is a manifestation of the same phenomenon. In their first study they adapted the AET

(Stanovich & West, 1997) so the problems could be classified into four categories based on the strength of the argument and the believability of the conclusion. However, in contrast to Stanovich and West they conclude that there is little support for the idea that belief bias in formal and informal reasoning is a unitary phenomenon, based on the lack of correlation across individuals in the extent of belief bias shown on the three tasks and the different interaction effects between believability and argument strength in the three tasks. They further support this assertion using the results of qualitative analyses of verbal justifications on the two informal reasoning tasks, because even though they found that conclusion believability strongly influenced assessments of argument strength, it had a relatively weak influence on these verbal justifications.

Belief bias and reasoning with emotional content

Belief bias is basically to do with the content – when the conclusion conflicts with general knowledge or experience, people prefer to accept conclusions that are believable over valid ones. In other words, it leads to the rejection of conclusions which are valid yet not believable and the acceptance of conclusions which are invalid but believable. The belief bias effect is usually significantly stronger for invalid syllogisms than it is for valid ones and this asymmetry suggests that people more readily accept conclusions congruent with their prior beliefs (be that prior knowledge, experience, or attitudes) without doing too much checking. If the conclusion is incongruent with their prior beliefs, they need to devote more attention to the problem to judge its validity.

There are several possible models that explain the failure of participants to accept conclusions that are valid but not believable. Most of them are rooted within dual-process theories, which hold there are two different systems of information processing – one based on quick, intuitive and heuristic responses and a second based on more deliberate, slow, and rule-based thinking (Ball & Stupple, 2016).

Ball and Stuppel (2016) review the main models explaining belief bias and place them into three general categories: (1) sequential dual-process models, such as the *selective scrutiny model* (Evans, Barston, & Pollard, 1983), *mental models theory* (Oakhill & Johnson-Laird, 1985), or the more recent version of the selective-scrutiny view known as the *selective-processing model* (Evans, 2007; Stuppel, Ball, Evans, & Kamal-, 2011); (2) parallel dual-processes models (Sloman, 1996; Stuppel & Ball, 2008; Thompson, Striener, Reikoff, Gunter, & Campbell, 2003), and the latest (3) hybrid models (De Neys, 2012).

Until recently, the main explanation for belief bias within dual-process theories was that the believability of a conclusion triggers fast heuristic processes which must be overridden by slow rule-based thinking. Because rule-based thinking is more effortful, many participants fail to come to the right solution (when it conflicts with their own beliefs) either because of a lack of cognitive abilities or of dispositions to exert cognitive effort.

However, recent findings suggest that sometimes rule-based reasoning can be quick, while belief-based reasoning can be slow (Newman, Gibb, & Thompson, 2017). Moreover, some recent findings using the conflict detection paradigm challenge the prevailing default interventionist model of dual-process theories in which intuitive response is a kind of default response. It seems that biased reasoners are not necessarily worse at conflict detection⁴ nor are they less sensitive to conflict than unbiased reasoners, but once the conflict is detected their System 2 thinking is not successfully completed, which may be because they lack the cognitive resources or motivation (De Neys, 2014; De Neys & Franssens, 2009).

⁴ This has been a traditional explanation – that people fail to detect the need for a more deliberate response and thus fail to engage System 2 thinking and rely simply on the heuristic response System 1 provides.

Although, to the best of our knowledge, this is the first attempt to use the belief bias paradigm for measuring myside bias, there have been several studies on the effect of emotional or controversial content on syllogistic reasoning, which are relevant to the discussion concerning our study. For example, in the 1940s, Janis and Frick (1941) examined how judgments of the logical validity of syllogisms are affected by emotional content that goes against one's beliefs. They found that there were more errors in judging the logical validity of syllogisms which had conclusions that were congruent but invalid (invalid believable) than those with congruent and valid conclusions; participants also showed more errors in judging the logical validity of incongruent and valid (valid unbelievable) items than they did judging incongruent invalid syllogisms. Similarly, Lefford (1946) found that most people tended to be more accurate in solving neutral syllogisms than emotionally charged syllogisms, and that there was little relationship between the ability to reason accurately in non-emotional and emotional situations. Moreover, both studies concluded that attitudes, beliefs, and feelings influenced reasoning toward prior beliefs, experience, and knowledge about the world. Generally, it was found that emotions have a negative effect on our reasoning ability (Blanchette, 2006; Blanchette & Richards, 2004; Trémolière & De Neys, 2014; Trémolière, De Neys, & Bonnefon, 2014). Although a few studies have also shown that emotion has an enhancing effect on syllogistic reasoning (Goel & Vartanian, 2011; Pauer, 2017). The effect of emotions in these studies is usually manipulated by the emotionally-laden content of the syllogisms or negative prior experience (such as sexual abuse).

However, although these studies used emotionally charged content and examined differences in performance between neutral and emotionally charged syllogisms, they did not directly measure the strength of the emotional content or the participants' actual

attitudes toward the emotionally charged content. For example, the conclusion “all women are prostitutes” is undoubtedly more emotional than “all women have blonde hair”. It is an open question as to what kind of emotions it aroused and one can argue that some people would even find the conclusion congruent with their attitudes towards women.

In the belief bias paradigm the believability of the conclusions is usually established in one of two ways: by using a separate sample to assess the believability of the conclusions (De Neys, Moyens, & Vansteenwegen, 2010; Eliades, Mansell, Stewart, & Blanchette, 2012; Goel & Vartanian, 2011) or by participants being asked to evaluate the validity and believability of conclusions separately (Trippas, Thompson, & Handley, 2017). In the belief bias paradigm it is important to address the issue of believability, and usually only conclusions that are undeniably believable to the majority people should be used. However, this is rather problematic especially where reasoning about controversial issues is concerned, which is what we are interested in, because if there is controversy then by definition there can be no general agreement. We purposefully included this controversy in our design and rather than controlling for the same level of believability in all participants we measured participants' prior attitudes to the controversial topic (i.e. abortions). Because all the participants assessed all the types of syllogisms (neutral, congruent with their attitude, and incongruent with their attitude), the believability of the conclusion should be irrelevant. Thus, we were not primarily interested in the conflict between validity and believability, but in the conflict between validity and prior attitudes, and so we examined the extent to which prior attitudes affected reasoning about controversial syllogisms. Bluntly put, we were not interested in

whether the participant would find the conclusion believable, but whether the controversial content would interact with their prior attitudes.

Studying informal reasoning using syllogisms

To study belief bias, researchers typically ensure the validity and believability of the conclusion conflict; in the myside bias paradigm the conflict is between the validity of the argument/conclusion and the person's attitudes to the topic. Usually, in the belief bias experimental paradigm, syllogisms are either produced or evaluated and the concentration is on the ones in which the validity conflicts with the believability (or perceived reality). In the myside bias paradigm more ecologically valid tasks are usually used where participants judge whether the arguments are consistent or inconsistent with their prior attitude. However, the use of real world arguments makes it hard to distinguish between the cognitive and motivational mechanisms in myside bias. In this paper, we were interested in investigating whether the motivational mechanism plays a crucial role in myside bias. If people differing only in prior attitudes, but not cognitive abilities (indexed by the ability to correctly solve neutral syllogisms), make more mistakes in syllogisms that are inconsistent with their beliefs, this would point to a motivational mechanism. It is more difficult to control for the equivalency of real-world arguments, so we used categorical syllogisms within the belief-bias paradigm so the consistency of the conclusion can be adjusted in line with prior attitudes to the controversial topic. The main aim of our study is not to investigate whether people with certain attitudes have inferior cognitive abilities, but whether they are motivated to ignore the logical structure of syllogisms that contradict their attitudes despite the structure being identical to that of syllogisms that reinforce their attitudes.

Our motivation for using more value-laden and controversial syllogisms was based on the fact that, apart from Baron's (1995) first study and the replication by Stanovich and West (2008), the majority of myside bias studies have used relatively non-controversial demographic information to examine how implicit theories relate to the way our group membership (e.g. social class, gender, religion, or smoking/drinking habits) affects our reasoning on these issues. This is also true of the Slovak research: Jurkovič (2014) studied myside bias using materials adapted from Stanovich and West (2008) (agreement with arguments on topics related to participants' smoking habits, drinking habits, and religion) and found significant myside bias that was unrelated to intelligence.

The primary goal of the current study is to examine myside bias in reasoning about issues directly relevant to the individual's attitudes, while the secondary goal is to replicate the myside effects in two Eastern European samples. In contrast to some other studies examining reasoning (Baron, 1995; Stanovich & West, 2008) in which participants were asked to evaluate the quality of the arguments on both sides of the debate, we chose to employ a belief bias paradigm using formal syllogistic reasoning to study myside bias in reasoning about abortions. Specifically, we expected to find people show a greater preference for (incorrectly) accepting as valid statements that are in line with their preferred conclusion, and vice versa, a greater preference for (incorrectly) rejecting statements that conflict with their preferred conclusion.

The idea was to merge these two paradigms and have participants evaluate the validity of conclusions that resembled real-life arguments about a controversial topic. It has already been shown that prior attitudes can influence the evaluation of arguments, but we wanted to examine how they also influence the reasoning process and the use of syllogisms allows for better control than arguments. In everyday speech we often use

statements – syllogisms, linear orderings, disjunctions, and if-then statements – but these are embedded in discourse and not labelled by premise and conclusion (Halpern, 2014). However, as we have already seen, people are affected by content and in an everyday context these statements can be used in a misleading way, either malevolently or through ignorance.

Method

Participants

We used convenience sampling to obtain our sample. In total, we collected data from 394 participants, but 7 of them were excluded from further analyses as they did not answer one or more items in the study. This left us with a final sample of 387 participants (77.3% women, age: $M = 21.15$, $SD = 2.90$). The participants were students of either Slovak ($n = 314$) or Polish origin ($n = 73$). In the demographics questionnaire, 13.7% of the participants indicated they had attended a course or seminar in formal logic. The Slovak sample consisted mainly of students taking various pedagogical majors and a few cognitive science students; the Polish sample contained students taking philosophy and economics majors.

Materials

Syllogistic reasoning tasks. The participants dealt with 36 categorical syllogisms. The problems were divided into three sets based on content, either in favour of a woman's right to abortion (*pro-choice syllogisms*) or the unborn child's right to live (*pro-life syllogisms*). The third set of tasks referred only to animals (*neutral syllogisms*). In each set, there were five syllogisms with logically valid conclusions and seven with

invalid conclusions⁵. Thus, six categories of syllogisms were created according to validity and content. Example items and the descriptive statistics for each category of syllogisms can be found in Table 1. All the syllogisms were balanced across the neutral, pro-life, and pro-choice categories, and they can be found in the Supplemental Materials.

General Social Survey (Jelen & Wilcox, 2003). To measure participant attitudes towards abortion we used the General Social Survey, which consists of six items pertaining to whether abortions should be legal under a series of increasingly serious circumstances: when the parents do not want another child; when the family is too poor to support another child; when the mother is single; when the pregnancy is the result of rape; when there is the possibility of a birth defect; and when the mother's life is in danger. The participants were asked to rate their agreement with every statement on a six-point scale ranging from 1 (absolutely disagree) to 6 (absolutely agree). The scores from the six questions were summed to produce a measure of participant attitudes on abortion. The scale showed the sample had good internal consistency (Cronbach's $\alpha = .86$). The mean reported score on the six items in our sample was 22.68 ($SD = 8.50$).

All the materials from this study are available in English in the Supplemental Materials. Materials in the original languages are available at osf.io/j9zu4.

Procedure

The materials were distributed separately to the students in the Slovak and Polish samples via an online survey. All the materials were translated by native

⁵ After the data collection had been completed, we found an error in the Slovak translation of one of the pro-choice valid syllogisms. As the error rendered the syllogism nonsensical, we decided to exclude the answers to it from both samples (to retain the same proportion of syllogistic tasks across the samples).

speakers and two versions of the survey were created – one in Slovak and the second in Polish. The participants first rated the six statements from the General Social Survey and then proceeded to answer 36 syllogisms in randomised order⁶. Prior to viewing the syllogisms, the participants were given one example item and received the instructions for solving the syllogistic problems. Specifically, they were told to always assume that the premises of the syllogisms were true and to only consider the conclusion of the syllogism to be valid if it followed logically from the two premises given⁷. Finally, they answered several demographic questions on age, gender, education, religious, and political affiliation, and on whether they had ever attended a course in formal logic.

⁶ The same random ordering of syllogisms was used for every participant.

⁷ The instructions read: Now you will read several syllogisms. Each syllogism consists of two premises (which are assumed to be true) and one conclusion following from them. Please indicate whether each conclusion is valid or invalid. Remember, the conclusion is valid only if it follows from the two premises. Now, please indicate whether the syllogisms below are valid or invalid.

Table 1. Example items and descriptive statistics of syllogisms in the six categories

	valid	invalid
neutral	All mastiffs are dogs. Some mastiffs are black. Some of the things which are black are dogs.	All mastiffs are dogs. Some dogs are black. Some of the things that are black are mastiffs
	<i>Mean accuracy: 72% ($\pm 22\%$)</i>	<i>Mean accuracy: 45% ($\pm 26\%$)</i>
pro-life	All foetuses should be protected. Some foetuses are human beings. Some human beings should be protected	All foetuses are human beings. Some human beings should be protected. Some of those who should be protected are foetuses.
	<i>Mean accuracy: 71% ($\pm 25\%$)</i>	<i>Mean accuracy: 45% ($\pm 25\%$)</i>
pro-choice	All women's rights should be supported. Some of women's rights are abortions. Some abortions should be supported.	All abortions are women's rights. Some of women's rights should be supported. Some of the things which should be supported are abortions.
	<i>Mean accuracy: 68% ($\pm 28\%$)</i>	<i>Mean accuracy: 46% ($\pm 25\%$)</i>

Note. The table contains example items for six categories of syllogisms employed in the study and presents mean proportions of syllogisms in every category answered correctly in the present sample with respective standard deviations in the parentheses.

Results

Our raw data are available at: osf.io/e7qzj. As there was an uneven number of syllogisms in the six possible categories, we calculated the proportion of correctly solved tasks for each participant in each category: neutral valid (NV), pro-choice valid (PChV), pro-life valid (PLV), neutral invalid (NI), pro-choice invalid (PChI), and pro-life invalid (PLI). Based on these proportions, we further computed several “*myside*

*bias indices*⁸. The myside bias index (MBI) for valid items was computed as a proportion of the PChV syllogisms subtracted from the proportion of PLV items answered correctly for every participant. For invalid items, the MBI was the proportion of PLI syllogisms subtracted from the proportion of PChI syllogisms that had been solved correctly. Finally, by summing the MBI for valid and invalid syllogisms, we computed an overall myside bias index.

As the syllogisms of every type are balanced across the logical formats, than if participants' responding is not influenced by their prior attitudes, it could be expected that they would be able to solve different types of syllogisms (e.g. PLV and PChV) with similar accuracy. Thus by subtracting the average accuracy on PChV syllogisms from that of the PLV syllogisms (and PLI from the PChI syllogisms), we get a clear measure of how much was participants responding affected by the content of the syllogism – e.g. whether participants accepted more pro-life valid than logically equivalent pro-choice valid conclusions. If our hypotheses concerning the effect of myside bias in syllogisms are correct, then participants with stronger pro-life attitudes should find it easier to solve the PLV and PChI syllogisms, as the conclusions of these syllogisms are in line with their prior attitudes. The opposite should be true for participants with pro-choice attitude. If myside bias has no effect on solving syllogisms, then the MBIs should not differ significantly across participants with different attitudes; however, if our reasoning is correct, then the more pro-life attitudes people have, the higher their indices should be. Conversely, the stronger pro-choice attitudes a person has, the lower his/her myside bias indices should be. Note, however, that the direction of MBI's is purely artificial. If we calculated the indices the other way around, then stronger pro-

⁸ As the preliminary analyses suggested different patterns in responses to the valid and invalid syllogisms, we decided to calculate myside bias indices for these two types of items separately, as well as combined into a single myside bias index

choice attitudes should be associated with higher myside bias indices, and stronger pro-life attitudes with lower myside bias indices. Higher positive values therefore do not indicate greater logical competence, but reflect that the individual responded more in line with what would be expected on the basis of myside bias effect among people with pro-life attitudes (and conversely, negative values reflect responding that would be expected on the basis on myside bias effect among people with pro-choice attitude). In the whole sample, means of all myside bias indices were very close to zero (overall MBI: $M = 0.040$, $SD = 0.441$; MBI for valid items: $M = 0.035$, $SD = 0.313$; MBI for invalid items: $M = 0.005$, $SD = 0.252$), indicating that on average, participants' responding was skewed neither in the direction of pro-life, nor pro-choice attitudes.

At the first step of our analysis we explored correlations among myside bias indices and their potential predictors. As can be seen from the Table 2, all three myside bias indices were correlated with abortion attitudes (higher scores reflect more pro-life attitude), even though the relationships were quite weak. Nevertheless, these correlations suggest that people with stronger pro-life attitude accepted more pro-life valid than pro-choice valid conclusions and rejected more pro-choice invalid than pro-life invalid conclusions, which is exactly the pattern of results which would be expected on the basis of myside bias. Furthermore, two of the indices were negatively correlated with the proportion of neutral valid and positively correlated with the proportion of neutral invalid syllogisms answered correctly. This seems to suggest that people who accepted more conclusions in line with pro-life attitude and rejected more conclusions that ran counter to pro-life attitude did score slightly higher on neutral invalid, but lower on neutral valid syllogisms.

Table 2. Correlations between myside bias indices and their potential predictors

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1. MBI	1							
2. MBI – valid	.829	1						
3. MBI – invalid	.721	.211	1					
4. sample	-.005	-.039	.039	1				
5. logic	.022	.051	-.025	.404	1			
6. neutral syllogisms	-.007	-.011	.001	.232	.366	1		
7. neutral valid	-.158	-.158	-.080	-.056	.133	.524	1	
8. neutral invalid	.127	.123	.069	.311	.301	.687	-.259	1
9. abortion attitude	.143	.106	.118	.011	-.143	-.065	-.130	.037

Note. $N = 387$. Correlation coefficients above $r = .100$ are significant at $p > .05$, coefficients above $r = .131$ are significant at $p > .01$, and above $r = .167$ are significant at $p > .001$. Correlations that appear in bold are significant. MBI = myside bias index.

Next, to further assess whether pre-existing attitudes toward abortion influenced the participants' ability to reason in the syllogistic tasks containing relevant statements over the variables related to logical abilities and the ability to solve syllogisms in general, we performed a series of regression analyses. In the first regression, overall myside bias index was entered as a dependent variable and the participant's abortion attitudes as the main predictor. Additionally, in the first step of the regression model we included previous experience of logic, the sample (Slovak vs. Polish participants), and accuracy on neutral syllogisms as possible predictors of the MBI. Abortion attitude, as measured by the General Social Survey, was then entered during the second step of the analysis to assess whether it predicted myside bias indices after other factors were accounted for. Summary of the regression analysis is presented in the Table 3. As can be seen from the results, neither experience of logic nor the ability to solve neutral syllogisms predicted overall myside bias index. In line with the predictions, the only significant predictor of myside bias responding was the abortion attitude. Thus, the

differences in prior attitudes toward abortion predicted whether participants responded more in line with pro-life or pro-choice conclusions in logically equivalent syllogistic reasoning tasks.

Table 3. Summary of results from hierarchical linear regression analysis with myside bias index as a dependent variable

	<i>B (SE)</i>	<i>β</i>	<i>p</i>
Myside bias index			
Step 1			
Constant	0.066 (0.096)		<i>p</i> = .496
Sample	-0.018 (0.063)	-.016	<i>p</i> = .782
Experience of logic	0.044 (0.075)	.035	<i>p</i> = .556
Neutral valid syllogisms	-0.025 (0.084)	-.016	<i>p</i> = .769
$R^2 = .001, p = .946$			
Step 2			
Constant	-0.120 (0.114)		<i>p</i> = .297
Sample	-0.032 (0.063)	-.028	<i>p</i> = .613
Experience of logic	0.077 (0.075)	.060	<i>p</i> = .307
Neutral syllogisms	-0.019 (0.083)	-.013	<i>p</i> = .816
Abortion attitude	0.008 (0.003)	.151	<i>p</i> = .003
$\Delta R^2 = .022, p = .003$			

Note. The table contains unstandardised regression coefficients (*B*'s) with their corresponding standard errors in parentheses, standardised regression coefficients (*β*'s), and levels of significance. The R^2 for the initial models and change in R^2 (ΔR^2) at every step of the model and corresponding significance levels are reported after each step. The sample was coded as: 0 = Slovak; 1 = Polish.

As the preliminary analyses suggested that the patterns of results pertaining to valid and invalid syllogisms differed, we decided to repeat the aforementioned regression model separately with MBI for valid and MBI for invalid syllogisms. The results are presented in the Table 4. Starting with the regression for the MBI in the valid syllogisms, during the first step of the analysis both previous experience of logic ($b = .114, p = .041$) and accuracy on NV syllogisms ($b = -.179, p < .001$) predicted the participants' myside bias index. Curiously, while a greater ability to solve the neutral versions of the syllogisms led to a lower myside bias, previous experience of logic was

actually associated with a higher MBI. Importantly, however, during the second step of the analysis, abortion attitudes ($b = .104, p = .041$) predicted a significant amount of variance over other factors in the analysis. This result indicates that participants who were more pro-life responded more accurately to PLV syllogisms that were in line with their prior attitudes than to PChV syllogisms which ran counter to their attitudes. The opposite was true for participants with more pro-choice attitudes. Importantly, as previous experience of logic and accuracy on neutral syllogisms was included in the analyses, it cannot be argued that the differences in susceptibility to myside bias were caused by differences in the pro-choice and pro-life participants' ability to solve syllogisms per se.

The results of the analysis of the MBI in the invalid items were quite different, as none of the variables in the first step of the model significantly predicted the participants' MBIs ($R^2 = .008, p = .354$). However, when attitudes toward abortion were entered as a predictor in the second step of the analysis, there was a significant change in the model fit. Attitude toward abortion thus emerged as the only significant predictor ($b = .109, p = .035$) of the myside bias index in invalid syllogisms. This indicates that the more pro-life participants were better at correctly rejecting the PChI conclusions, which conflicted with their attitudes, than the PLI conclusions, which likewise did not follow on logically from the premises but were in line with participant's attitudes. The opposite was true for the more pro-choice participants. The results of both regression analyses are therefore in line with our predictions. However, it should be noted that while the abortion attitudes significantly predicted both myside bias indices, the proportion of variance explained by them, as well as other factors in the analyses, was quite low. It is therefore quite possible that there are other variables that play an

important role in the ability to answer pro-attitudinal and counter-attitudinal syllogistic reasoning tasks, but these were not investigated in the present study.

Table 4. Summary of results from hierarchical linear regression analyses with myside bias indices as dependent variables

	<i>B (SE)</i>	<i>β</i>	<i>p</i>
Myside bias index – valid items			
Step 1			
Constant	0.219 (0.055)		<i>p</i> = .001
Sample	-0.076 (0.044)	-.095	<i>p</i> = .085
Experience of logic	0.103 (0.050)	.114	<i>p</i> = .041
Neutral valid syllogisms	-0.256 (0.073)	-.179	<i>p</i> < .001
<i>R</i> ² = .038, <i>p</i> = .002			
Step 2			
Constant	0.120 (0.073)		<i>p</i> = .103
Sample	-0.082 (0.044)	-.102	<i>p</i> = .064
Experience of logic	0.118 (0.051)	.130	<i>p</i> = .021
Neutral valid syllogisms	-0.240 (0.073)	-.168	<i>p</i> = .001
Abortion attitude	0.004 (0.002)	.104	<i>p</i> = .041
$\Delta R^2 = .010, p = .041$			
Myside bias index – invalid items			
Step 1			
Constant	-0.027 (0.026)		<i>p</i> = .297
Sample	0.027 (0.037)	.042	<i>p</i> = .462
Experience of logic	-0.047 (0.042)	-.064	<i>p</i> = .259
Neutral invalid syllogisms	0.074 (0.054)	.075	<i>p</i> = .169
<i>R</i> ² = .008, <i>p</i> = .354			
Step 2			
Constant	-0.098 (0.042)		<i>p</i> = .021
Sample	0.022 (0.037)	.035	<i>p</i> = .539
Experience of logic	-0.032 (0.042)	-.043	<i>p</i> = .450
Neutral invalid syllogisms	0.066 (0.054)	.067	<i>p</i> = .218
Abortion attitude	0.003 (0.002)	.109	<i>p</i> = .035
$\Delta R^2 = .011, p = .035$			

Note. The table contains unstandardised regression coefficients (*B*'s) with their corresponding standard errors in parentheses, standardised regression coefficients (*β*'s),

and levels of significance. The R^2 for the initial models and change in R^2 (ΔR^2) at every step of the model and corresponding significance levels are reported after each step. The sample was coded as: 0 = Slovak; 1 = Polish.

As the myside bias indices computed in this study represent an unprecedented way of analysing the effect of myside bias on solving logical syllogisms, we have also decided to complement the regression analyses above with more traditional analytic approach based on simple proportions of syllogisms in every category answered correctly. Specifically, we divided participants into three attitude groups based on the tertile split of their responses on the General social survey and performed a mixed-design analysis of variance, with one between-subject (*attitude groups*: pro-choice, neutral, pro-life) and two within-subject factors (*syllogism validity*: valid, invalid; *syllogism content*: pro-choice, neutral, pro-life). The results of this analysis are presented in the supplementary material. Briefly, the only significant difference among the three attitudinal groups was in the proportion of PChV syllogisms answered correctly, where pro-life oriented participants scored lower than people with neutral or pro-choice attitude.

The results of the ANOVA could be taken as evidence that the strongest myside bias may have occurred among pro-life oriented participants who presumably had difficulty accepting valid pro-choice arguments, as these ran counter to their attitudes. However, it should be noted that these results are less efficient way of testing for myside bias effect than the regressions analyses reported above, as the proportions of syllogisms in every category answered correctly could be heavily influenced by a range of broad factors, such as the general intelligence. In comparison, the analyses based on myside bias indices control for such influences, as they merely reflect the propensity to respond more correctly to syllogisms which are in line with the person's previous

attitudes rather than to items which are in conflict with them, and do not reflect a specific ability to solve syllogisms per se.

Still, it is interesting to note that the only significant difference between attitude groups in analysis of variance was in the accuracy on pro-choice syllogisms. One possibility which we considered for these results is that the participants in our sample may have been very pro-life oriented in general. If the myside bias effect in syllogisms led to greater difficulty in accepting conclusions which ran counter to the person's prior attitudes, then the overall sample bias toward pro-life attitudes may explain why we only found the significant differences in pro-choice syllogisms. We return to this point in the discussion.

Discussion and Conclusions

The main aim of our study was to explore whether people are more inclined to accept a conclusion that confirms their prior beliefs and reject one they personally object to even when both follow the same logic. Most of the prior research in this area has relied on informal reasoning; in this study, however, we applied a formal reasoning paradigm to distinguish between cognitive and motivational mechanisms leading to myside bias in reasoning on value-laden topics (in this case abortions).

The reason for this new methodological approach was to obtain an objective measure of arguments' validity. While in the typical myside bias paradigm people evaluate real-life statements which may differ in the strength or validity of an argument they present, in the syllogistic reasoning paradigm the validity of the conclusion is determined solely by its relation to the premises. This allows to specifically measure the influence of prior attitudes on reasoning while keeping other factors, such as the reasoning ability and argument validity, constant. Moreover, by using a within-

participant design where all participants received the same forms of syllogisms representing all six types (valid and invalid neutral, pro-life, and pro-choice), we could directly compare the effect of their beliefs (measure separately) on reasoning about different types of content.

To directly assess the effect of prior attitudes, we created two myside bias indices.⁹ These allowed us to ascertain whether participants responded in line with their attitudes – it was hypothesized that pro-life participants would find it easier to accept PLV syllogisms than PChV syllogisms, and to reject PChI rather than PLI syllogisms, while the opposite would be true for pro-choice participants. Note that regardless of the actual believability of the syllogisms (which may technically have differed across different items), all participants answered the same syllogisms, so any differences observed in the accuracy of the same set of syllogisms could not have been caused by differences in the believability of the syllogism conclusion per se. Thus, we hypothesized that any observed effect would be caused by “acceptability”, in the sense that the pro-life conclusions would seem more “acceptable” to the pro-life participants, (and the opposite would be true for the pro-choice participants) rather than the believability being a characteristic of the syllogism itself. In our research this is presumably dependent on participants’ prior attitudes.

⁹ We created two myside indices, for the valid and invalid syllogisms separately. The main reason for using two separate indices was the previous finding that reasoning about invalid syllogisms is generally more difficult, because they are usually more complex. According to Halpern (2014), negations further complicate the problems because of a basic cognitive principle: negative information (no, not) is more difficult to process than positive information, in part because it seems to place additional demands on the working memory. In addition, the general response bias to accept conclusions meant it seemed reasonable to analyse the valid and invalid syllogisms separately. The indices do not tell us about the ability to solve syllogisms; their main strength is that they allow us to control for all the individual characteristics (such as logical ability) and thus they represent a more robust measure of myside bias.

Using a within-participant design in which the three types of syllogisms are balanced is suitable for establishing the effect of prior attitudes on reasoning and logic. Furthermore, we believe that the use of syllogistic reasoning paradigm effectively deals with the two problems discussed in the myside bias literature that are associated with having arguments of equivalent quality on both sides. Firstly, the use of syllogisms allows us to construct arguments that follow exactly the same form, but have different conclusions – that are either congruent or incongruent with an attitude on any controversial topic. Secondly, by measuring the attitudes separately, we were able to measure the strength of the attitude and its effect on reasoning.

The main finding of our analyses, then, is that myside bias does indeed affect formal reasoning even after controlling for logical abilities (solving neutral valid/invalid syllogisms) and experience of logic both for valid and invalid syllogisms.

While the effect of prior attitudes on reasoning was not particularly strong, we observed that participants did have difficulties with accepting logically valid conclusions that conflicted with their beliefs, and rejecting ones that they personally agreed with. It seems that myside bias on the issue blinded participants from evaluating the logical validity of the syllogism. This explanation is supported by findings showing that performance on the inconsistent syllogisms were lower than on the consistent syllogisms, particularly among participants who endorsed pro-life attitudes.

However, besides showing that myside bias also affects reasoning about controversial topics, we obtained some peculiar results concerning the valid syllogisms. Experience of logic and logical ability (solving neutral syllogisms) were both significant predictors of myside bias index (i.e. the answers were more in line with a pro-life attitude). Our results (Table 4) seem to suggest that the more syllogisms the person

correctly solves, the lower the score in the myside bias index, i.e. the more a person's answers are in line with the pro-choice answers. On the other hand, experience of logic was another significant predictor of myside bias index, and, rather unexpectedly, it showed that the more previous experience of logic people had, the more they tended to respond in line with a pro-life attitude. We can only offer speculative explanations for this result. This result could have been confounded by the sample (although the sample was not a significant predictor of the MBI in either case, there was marginal significance where the valid syllogisms were concerned). The Polish participants generally had more experience of logic, owing mainly to the fact that part of the Polish sample had been recruited from the philosophy student population. It is possible that philosophy students, despite being familiar with solving syllogisms, could have stronger religious attitudes. But it is also quite possible that the results were confounded by an underlying factor that was not measured. Another unanswered question is why this result occurred only in the valid syllogisms; the results from the invalid syllogisms were more consistent with our expectations. As we have already mentioned, reasoning about invalid syllogisms is generally more difficult, but it is difficult to pinpoint exactly how this might have influenced the results observed.

What we can say is that our results also seem to suggest that not only was experience of logic not helpful in overcoming the disposition to reject undesirable conclusions, it was associated with giving responses in line with pro-life attitudes. It could be the case that experience of logic makes participants more certain when reasoning about valid congruent syllogisms (which are generally easier to reason about anyway), but not such that they were actually able to reason better, which would have resulted in there being more correctly solved incongruent syllogisms.

Some previous studies have found that attending logic classes or classes on abstract logical principles undertaken in laboratory conditions do not improve performance on a reasoning task (Wason selection task) (Cheng, Holyoak, Nisbett, & Oliver, 1986). However, Evans, Newstead, Allen, and Pollard (1994) conducted three experiments using syllogisms and concluded that belief bias may be reduced, but not eliminated, by instructional manipulation. Similarly, Macpherson and Stanovich (2007) found instruction had some effect, but while the decontextualised instruction seemed to help with the argument generation task, it had no effect on the experiment evaluation task, and only a small effect on the syllogistic reasoning task. It is possible that instructional training may be more beneficial to statistical inference than to logical reasoning (Evans et al., 1994). It is remarkable that receiving instruction or attending formal logic courses (as in the case of the philosophy students in the Polish sample) does not eliminate myside bias completely, and shows how powerful this bias is. Although simply teaching participants to assume the premises are true is not enough, this does not necessarily mean that more extensive training would be futile. In our study we only asked whether participants had attended a formal course of logic; we did not check the nature or length of the course, nor whether the participants had attended it recently or whether they had learnt some formal ways of solving syllogisms, for instance with the help of Venn diagrams. Future research should focus more on the aspects of debiasing strategies that succeed in transferring the effects to real life.

An inability to use learnt strategies to solve problems, as can sometimes be seen in cases where people of normal or high intelligence fail heuristics and biases tasks and thus show a high degree of irrationality, can be a manifestation of the difference between optimal and typical performance (Stanovich, 2011). School intelligence and knowledge tests are usually taken under conditions of optimal performance – students

know what kind of knowledge is being tested and (usually) try to do their best in the test. Many experiments involving rationality tasks are used to test typical performances and the participants often do not know what exactly is being tested. As studies involving instructional manipulation (Evans et al., 1994) show, more explicit instruction aimed at optimal performance is indeed helpful, but still not sufficient to completely eliminate the strong biases we have, so it is probably safe to say that even formal school training often fails to produce strong or long-term effects in real life. Also as recent studies have shown, the biased responses are not necessarily caused by the inability to detect the conflict between intuitive and normative responses, but rather by the inability to successfully suppress our intuitive response (De Neys, 2012, 2014). Although our results do not enable us to say whether our participants were aware of the conflict between the logic and their attitudes, they do suggest that motivational factors play a role in the double standards we use to evaluate conclusions incongruent with our attitudes. Therefore, it seems quite plausible that even if the participants did detect any conflict, they were not able to inhibit their *myside* (intuitive) response and thus displayed a failure of inhibition (De Neys, 2012).

It is noteworthy that our sample seems to be more conservative than American samples (Smith & Son, 2013). When we compared the attitudes of our participants with the results summarised by Smith and Son (2013), we can see that in our sample there was slightly more reluctance to accept abortion for each reason. For example, in the American sample approval of abortion was highest when the woman's health was seriously endangered (87.0% across all years, 1972–2012), while 68.7% of our participants indicated they agreed with abortion in this case. In both samples approval of abortion was lowest if the child was conceived out of wedlock, and here the

difference was even more pronounced (42.0% in the American sample vs. 28.2% in our sample)¹⁰.

One of the limitations of our study was that despite our attempt to link myside bias to specific political and religious affiliations and to verify whether conservatives use more intuitive thinking strategies and thus yield more to belief bias, we were not able to run all the analyses. More than half the Slovak participants refused to state their political affiliation (68.4% indicated that either they were not interested in politics or did not wish to answer) and because we allowed the participants to self-identify we received answers such as: middle (1%), democrat without party affiliation (0.6%), Christian (0.3%) and Stoic (0.3%). We lacked familiarity with Polish politics so we did not ask Polish participants this question.

The self-identification of religion did not prove very helpful either – in the Polish sample there was virtually no variability as 100% of the participants indicated that they belonged to the Roman Catholic Church. While the Slovak sample was more varied¹¹, the self-identifications did not tell us anything about the strength of their faith, which would probably have been more informative than church affiliation.

Therefore in future research we would like to include other moderators of motivated reasoning, such as personal epistemology (Kardash & Scholes, 1996; Schommer, 1990; Schraw, Bendixen, & Dunkle, 2002) or the need for closure

¹⁰ The participants in Smith and Son (2013) responded using yes/no answers to the six attitude questions. The percentage of agreement in our sample was calculated by adding together the participants who answered completely agree and slightly agree.

¹¹ 17.4% indicated they had no religion, 68.8% were Roman Catholic, 3.7% were Protestant, 1.6% Greek Catholic/Orthodox, 4% indicated another Christian religion, 0.6% indicated some other religion (Hinduism, Buddhism, Pagan, Slavic, Nordic, etc.) and 0.9 % indicated that they had some sort of idiosyncratic faith without any official religious affiliation.

(Cacioppo & Petty, 1982), or to examine the differences between belief-driven versus knowledge-driven participants (Klaczynski, 2000). For example Klaczynski (2000) found that after being “presented with a challenging task, knowledge-driven adolescents, motivated by the desire to look beyond superficial task characteristics, were more likely to decontextualize beliefs from reasoning than adolescents whose predominant goal was theory preservation” (p. 1361).

Despite these limitations, our results show why debates about controversial issues often seem so futile – our values can blind us to acknowledging the same logic in our opponent's arguments if the values underlying these arguments offend our own.

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